

Electronic Spectra of Binuclear Complexes of Cobalt and Chromium

Satya Brata Saha

Electronic absorption spectra of tetraethylenediamine-diol-dicobaltic bromide, tetraethylenediamine-diol-dichromic bromide and hexabenzylamine-triol-dicobalt trichloride have been measured. The spectra have been explained on the basis of the molecular orbital theory.

Although the application of molecular orbital formulation to complexes of transition metals has been clear enough, since van Vleck's¹ classic works, only a minute number of works have been attempted to give a complete calculation of energy levels. On the other-hand the MO theory provides a better description of the bonding situation in some binuclear complexes containing transition metals and provides a ready explanation of otherwise puzzling aspect of their molecular structure². While it will certainly not be possible for a long time to come to figure out the energy level for such binuclear complexes, it should be possible to determine their situation from the measurements of absorption spectra. The aim of the present paper is to discuss the absorption spectra of some of binuclear complexes of cobalt and chromium on the basis of the theory of molecular orbital.

I(a). *Tetraethylenediamine-diol-dicobaltic Bromide* :

This compound taken as a whole has D_{2h} symmetry but the local symmetry of each Co^{+3} ion is only³ C_{2v} . The set of six σ -bonds (four σ -bonds coming from the ligands L and two σ -bonds coming from two OH^- ligands) transforms as $3A_1 + B_1 + 2B_2$. As the metal orbitals in C_{2v} transform under $4A_1 + A_2 + 2B_1 + 2B_2$ we find that if each ligand donates two electrons, there will remain three vacant orbitals, namely $A_1 + A_2 + B_1$, provided we disregard the antibonding σ -orbitals.

The complex is composed of two units, each having its local C_{2v} symmetry, consequently the 'vacant' wavefunction of the entire system will transform under $A_g + B_{1u} + B_{1g} + A_u + B_{2g} + B_{2u}$. As two OH^- radicals have electron pairs available for π -bonding, the two π -orbitals in D_{2h} transform as $B_{1g} + B_{2u}$. Since these last two orbitals can combine with the 'vacant'

1. Van Vleck, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1935, 3, 303; *ibid.*, 1935, 3, 807.
2. Dunitz and Orgel, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 2594.
3. C. J. Ballhausen, *Introduction to Ligand Field Theory* (McGraw Hill, 1962).

orbitals of symmetry B_{1g} and B_{2u} , we get for complete schematic binding pattern, starring the antibonding orbitals

$$(B_{1g})(B_{3u})[(A_g)(A_u)(B_{1u})(B_{2g})](B_{1g}^*)(B_{3u}^*) \quad \dots (1)$$

From group theory, it is not of course possible to get the absolute situation of the orbitals, but it seems that the energy of the non-bonding orbitals (in square brackets) should be flanked respectively by the binding and antibonding orbitals. In these orbitals we shall, therefore, place the four electrons from the π -bonding as well as the d -electrons from the metal ions. Since the complex in which both the cobalt ions are trivalent, the four electrons from π -bondings and the 12- d electrons from the two metal ions will just fill all the orbitals listed in (1). Consequently we do not expect any crystal field transitions involving any vacant non-bonding orbitals. The longest wavelength band will arise when the electron makes a transition from B_{1g}^* or B_{3u}^* orbital to antibonding σ -orbitals of symmetry A_u , B_{2u} or B_{1u} . Transitions from B_{1g}^* will have "odd-even" character and so will be of high intensity, while that from B_{3u}^* will have "odd-odd" character and hence will be absent or will appear with extremely low intensity. So we should expect very strong bands for this binuclear complex compared to its father mono-nuclear complex. Fig. 1 represents the absorp-

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of $[\text{en}_2 \text{Co} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{OH}]\text{Br}_2$ and $\left[\text{en}_2 \text{Co} \begin{array}{c} \text{OH} \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{Co} \quad \text{Co} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{OH} \end{array} \text{en}_2 \right] \text{Br}_4$ in water.

tion spectra of this complex and shows absorption bands with peaks at $19,050 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $26,500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and one band above $30,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ having extinctions of 270, 220 and above 10, 00 respectively. Evidently these bands cannot be associated with pure $d-d$ bands; their intensity

suggests that these are weakly Laporte allowed bands. So these bands may arise from transitions from B_{1g}^* orbital to antibonding σ -orbital.

II(a). *Tetraethylenediamine-diol-dichromic Bromide*

In this complex we will have four electrons for π -bonding and (2×3) 6- d electrons from chromium. These ten electrons will, therefore, fill up five MO's of (1) i.e., the electronic configuration of the complex will be

$$(B_{1g})^2(B_{3u})^2[(A_g)^2(A_u)^2(B_{1u})^2(B_{2g})^0](B_{1g}^*)^0(B_{3u}^*)^0$$

Since the non-bonding orbitals will be incompletely filled absorption may arise due to electron transition between the non-bonding orbitals. Consequently we expect that the absorption spectra will show low intensity bands comparable to the crystal field bands, since the non-bonding orbitals are essentially metal d -orbitals.

In Fig. 2, are shown the absorption spectra of $[\text{en}_2 \text{Cr H}_2\text{O.OH}] \text{Br}_2^{IIb}$ and

absorption bands with peaks at $19,300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $25,950 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ having extinctions of 60 and 45 respectively. The binuclear complex on the other hand shows absorption peaks at

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of $[\text{en}_2 \text{Cr H}_2\text{O.OH}] \text{Br}_2$ and $\left[\text{en}_2 \text{Cr} \begin{array}{c} \text{OH} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{Cr} \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{OH} \end{array} \text{Cr en}_2 \right] \text{Br}_4$ in water.

$18,900 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $25,800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and one absorption above $36,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The extinction of these two bands are 126, 95 and above 500 respectively. Compared to the corresponding cobalt complexes, the extinctions of the bands of the binuclear chromium complexes are rather

low indicating that these are probably weakly allowed symmetry forbidden bands. MO description predicts that there should be some low intensity transitions in binuclear chromium complexes involving non-bonding orbitals. The low intensity bands experimentally observed may be associated with these transitions involving non-bonding orbitals. The high intensity high frequency band is probably associated with the electron transition from non-bonding orbitals to antibonding π -orbital of oxygen. That is, this band is basically a metal ligand charge transfer band. Such charge transfer is possible in mononuclear complex also. This is indicated by slowly rising portion of the absorption spectrum of the mononuclear complex above $36,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

In this complex, the local symmetry is still C_{2v} , but the complex will have no center of symmetry and the symmetry functions cannot be labelled with u or g symbols. The reducible representation of σ -bonding is found, as before, to contain the irreducible representation $3A_1 + B_1 + 2B_2$ and the metal orbitals transform as

$$4A_1 + A_2 + 2B_1 + 2B_2$$

In this case the six ligands supply 12 electrons for σ -bond formation, while in the two bridge case the ligands supplied 16-electrons. Consequently the two more metal orbitals will remain vacant and will be lumped together as non-bonding orbitals. As only two of the OH^- groups can enter into π -bond formation to give B_1 and B_2 orbitals, the electrons from the third OH^- radical must pair with one of the non-bonding orbitals to give a weak bond. The electron configuration will therefore be

$$(B_1^a)(B_2^a)[(A_1^b)(A_1^b)(B_1^b)(B_2^b)](B_1^{a*})(B_2^{a*})(A_2^\omega)(A_2^{\omega*})$$

in which the superscript 'a' and 'b' refer to orbitals centered primarily on OH^- and metal respectively. The superscript ω refers to the weak bond formed between one of the OH^- radicals and one of the non-bonding metal orbital. These orbitals can be filled by 20 electrons, whereas only 18 electrons are available. The $A_2^{\omega*}$ orbital will remain vacant and transition can take place from the filled orbitals to this orbital. Since all transitions are Laporte allowed (i.e., no g or u character for any of the levels) quite a number of transitions may appear with appreciable intensity.

Fig. 3, shows the absorption spectra of this complex in the polycrystalline state. It can be observed that no less than five absorption peaks can be located in the low frequency region.

Fig. 3. Absorption spectra of $\left[\left(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2 \right)_3 \text{Co} \begin{array}{c} \text{OH} \\ \diagup \quad \diagdown \\ \text{O} \quad \text{O} \\ \diagdown \quad \diagup \\ \text{OH} \end{array} \text{Co} \left(\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \right)_3 \right] \text{Cl}_3$ in polycrystalline state.

EXPERIMENTAL

The absorption spectra in solution were measured with Beckman spectrophotometer Model DU. The spectra in the solid state were measured in a crystal spectrophotometer described previously⁴.

Preparation of the complex: The compound⁵⁻¹⁰ Ia was prepared from *cis*-hydroxo-aquodiethylenediamine cobalt dithionate by the method of Dubsy. The compound Ib was prepared from *trans*-dichlorodiethylenediamine cobaltic chloride according to the method of Werner. The compound¹¹⁻¹³ IIa was prepared from *cis*-hydroxo-aquodiethylenediamine chromic bromide by the method of Pfeiffer. Compound¹⁴ III was prepared following the method of Percival and Wardlaw.

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Dept. of Chemistry,
University College of Science,
Calcutta-9.

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